

FACILE SYNTHESIS OF GRAPHENE SURFACE-MODIFIED ALUMINUM POWDER WITH LOW INFRARED EMISSIVITY AND EXCELLENT ANTICORROSIVE PERFORMANCE

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ABSTRACT

Aluminum powder, common metal filler, is always used to prepare low infrared emissivity coating. However, a higher powder content in the coating usually lead to the bad anticorrosive performance. Considering the good anticorrosive performance of graphene, here we demonstrate a novel and facile method to prepare graphene surface-modified aluminum powder, using 3-aminopropylphosphoric acid as "link" agent. Firstly, graphene oxide, prepared by Hummers method, was functionalized by reacting with 3-aminopropylphosphoric acid at 95 °C. The remained -PO(OH)₂ functional groups on modified GO were then reacted with aluminum to obtain graphene-modified aluminum powder. The Fourier transform infrared spectra (FT-IR), X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS), X-ray diffraction (XRD) and scanning electron microscopy (SEM) were used to verify the structures of the resultants. From all experimental data, it is clear that the aluminum powders were successfully coated with a layer of graphene via Al-O-P bonds. The graphene-modified aluminum powder was highly efficient in preparing lower infrared emissivity coatings with excellent anticorrosive performance. The coating with 40% graphene-modified aluminum powder exhibited a low infrared emissivity (0.406) at spectral range of 8-14 μm, and remaining the appearance after 500 hours of salt spray corrosion test, while the color of coating with the original aluminum powder has been changed in only 300 hours.

1 INTRODUCTION

Aluminum has been applied in a wide range of industrial applications due to its excellent thermal and electrical conductivity. It also recently became a metal of choice as filler in low infrared emissivity coatings^[1]. Extensive works have been reported so far^[2-3] on the preparation of low infrared emissivity coatings using aluminum powder as the filler. The effects of filler content, the diameter of the filler and the thickness of the coating on the infrared emissivity were also studied. It was clearly reported that the volume content of the aluminum powder was always at a high level for getting a coating with lower emissivity. However, the higher aluminum powder content in the coating usually lead to the bad anticorrosive performance. Because the low infrared emissivity paint film also acts as a physical barrier between outside environment and the substrate, the anticorrosive performance of the low infrared emissivity coatings is crucial when it was applied in outside circumstances. Anticorrosion paints often consist of an organic binder and an anticorrosive pigment dispersed in the binder. An anticorrosive pigment is made up of chemical materials with corrosive-inhibiting properties. Chromate is the most common prominent anticorrosive pigments. However, its toxicity and harmfulness to the environment limit the application in the anticorrosion paints. For this reason, it is being replaced by phosphate, molybdate, borate or vanadate (IV) pigments^[4-7]. Nevertheless, the infrared emissivity of the coating will rise when these anticorrosive pigments are applied to increase the anticorrosive performance. Therefore, an effective method to form the expectable low infrared emissivity coating having good anticorrosive property is urgently required.

Graphene-based materials have attracted much interest for their unique features, such as high thermal conductivity, electrical conductivity, high strength and chemical stability^[8-9]. The surface of graphene, a one atom thick sheet of carbon, can be randomly decorated with oxygen to create graphene oxide. The graphene oxide has a significant impact on the chemical, pharmaceutical and electronic industries. It has been anticipated as a promising novel anticorrosion coating due to the good anticorrosive performance^[10]. As effective filler in paint, graphene could provide an ultra-strong, non-corrosive coating for a wide range of industrial applications. This contrasting property is attributed to the structure of graphene oxide films which consist of millions of small flakes stacked randomly on top of each other but leave nano-sized capillaries between them. Water molecules tend to be inside these nanocapillaries and can drag small atoms and molecules along. It can be supposed that if the aluminum particle was coated with graphene, the composite structure could not only exhibit good anticorrosive property but also low infrared emissivity. However, the study of graphene/aluminum composites, especially its low infrared emissivity and anticorrosive property, is still an emerging field. In this paper, the graphene surface-modified aluminum (G-Al) powder was synthesized and subsequently demonstrated by the Fourier transform infrared spectra (FT-IR), X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS), X-ray diffraction (XRD) and field emitting scanning electron microscopy (FE-SEM). Coating with the graphene surface-modified flake aluminum as the filler was prepared, the infrared emissivity and the anticorrosive property were also studied.

2 EXPERIMENTAL

2.1 Materials

Natural graphite powder was purchased from Huadong Graphite Factory (Pingdu, China) with an average diameter of 48 μm . Aluminum powder was purchased from Beijing Chemical Factory (China). 3-aminopropylphosphonic acid (APPSA) was obtained from TCI. All the other reagents and solvents were purchased from Beijing Chemical Factory (China) and were used without further purification.

2.2 Preparation of the -PO(OH)₂ functionalized graphene oxide (GO-P)

The synthetic procedure of GO-P is shown in Figure 1. Firstly, GO was prepared from natural graphite by modified Hummers method. The as-prepared GO was first dispersed in deionized water to form a concentration of 1 mg ml⁻¹ suspension by ultrasonication for 2 h. Subsequently, a certain amount of APPSA was added. The mixture was refluxed with magnetic stirring at 95 °C for 20 hours, then dialyzed with cellulose ester dialysis membrane (MWCO is 500~1000 D) in deionized water for 7

days to remove the unreacted 3-aminopropylphosphoric acid. The mixture was dried in vacuum oven at 60 °C for 24 h.

Figure 1: The preparation route of GO-P and G-Al

2.3 Synthesis of graphene-modified aluminum (G-Al) powder

The synthesis sketch for G-Al powder is also shown in Figure 1. The aluminum powder was washed by ethanol before dispersing in water. A certain amount of GO-P was dispersed in water by ultrasonication and added in the suspension of aluminum powder. The mixture was then heated to 40 °C and kept stirring for 4 h. The liquid mixture was then filtered and washed with water repeatedly to remove the unreacted GO-P. The filter cake was heated at 120 °C in vacuum oven for 24 h to get G-Al powder.

2.4 Preparation of lower infrared emissivity coating

Al substrate (10 cm × 10 cm, thickness 2 mm), properly cleaned at room temperature by ethanol, was used as the coating substrate to measure the infrared emissivity and anticorrosive property. Firstly, a fixed amount of polyurethane (PU) and the G-Al powder were mixed and painted on Al substrate by a spray technique (SATA, Germany) using an accurate speed motor and appropriate pressure. At the same time the PU/Al powder coating was prepared to comparison test. The weight concentration of the G-Al powder (or Al powder) was 40%. The coatings were dried in an oven at 60 °C for 24 h, and the thickness of coating was 40~50 μm.

2.5 Characterization

The compositions of GO and GO-P were recorded with XPS and FT-IR. XPS analysis was performed with an AXIS-Ultra instrument from Kratos Analytical using monochromatic Al/Kα radiation and low energy electron flooding for charge compensation. The data were converted into VAMAS file format and imported into CASA XPS software package for manipulation and curve fitting. The FTIR spectra of the GO and GO-P were recorded by Magna 750 FT-IR Spectrometer. The crystalline structure were analyzed by XRD spectra. XRD analysis was conducted with a Rigaku D/max-rB diffractometer using Cu/Kα radiation ($\lambda = 1.5406 \text{ \AA}$); the scan rate was 6° per minute, ranging from 10° to 60°. The morphologies of the G-Al composite particle and Al particle were examined by field emission scanning electron microscopy (FE-SEM, Apollo-300 OXFORD Co).

The coating thickness was measured using a digital magnetism thickness instrument (China), with a standard instrumental error of $\pm 1 \mu\text{m}$. The infrared emissivity value of the sample within 8~14 μm were measured by SR-5000 infrared emissometer (Shanghai Institute of Technological Physics, China). The corrosion behavior of the coatings was measured by 500 h salt spray test. The test is performed by exposure the sample in a testing chamber and carried out using as corrosive medium a continuously spray the mist of 5% aqueous solution of sodium chloride at a temperature of 35 °C. Compressed, humidified air is used to spray the solution.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

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3.1 Functionalization of GO

The functionalization of GO with APPSA was achieved via the nucleophilic substitution reaction between the epoxy group of GO and the amine group of APPSA. To confirm the structure of the obtained products, a series of characterization were applied. Fig. 2 shows the XRD spectra of GO and GO-P. The characteristic diffraction peak of GO is 11.1° , the interlayer distance is about 0.80 nm, which is calculated by Bragg equation $2d\sin\theta=\lambda$. The distance is larger than that of pristine graphite (~ 0.34 nm) due to the presence of oxygenated functional groups on carbon sheets. After reaction with APPSA, the peak shifts to 10.3° with an interlayer distance of 0.86 nm. The enlarged interlayer distance of GO confirms the intercalation of APPSA.

Figure 2: XRD patterns of GO and GO-P

The functionalization of GO with APPSA is further confirmed by FT-IR spectra (Fig.3). The peaks at 809 cm^{-1} can be assigned to the C-O vibration of the epoxy groups in GO. After reacting with APPSA, the peak of 809 cm^{-1} disappears in the spectrum of P-GO. Furthermore, the appearance of the peak at 1240 cm^{-1} (free P=O stretching vibration) provides more evidence for the functionalization of GO.

Figure 3: FT-IR spectra of GO and GO-P

XPS is also used to characterize the interaction between GO and APPSA (Fig. 4). Compared to GO, the survey of P-GO shows the peaks of P_{2p} and P_{2s} , indicating that the APPSA has been grafted to the GO surface (Fig.4a), which is consistent with the FT-IR results. Besides, the peak of N_{1s} becomes more prominent in the spectra of P-GO (Fig.4a). The N_{1s} of P-GO can be fitted into two line shapes

with binding energies of 399.4 and 401.4 eV, which are attributed to -C-NH-C- and -C-NH₂, respectively (Fig.4b). The presence of -C-NH-C peak further suggests the covalent grafting of GO with APPSA. It is concluded that -C-NH-C- bands were formed by the reaction between the epoxy groups and the amine groups, demonstrating the APPSA had a strong interaction with the GO surface instead of just being physically deposited.

Figure 4: XPS spectra of GO and GO-P (a) XPS wide scan spectra (b) N1s spectra

3.2 Microstructure of graphene-modified aluminum powder

The morphology of the prepared graphene functionalized aluminum composites and aluminum powder were observed by FE-SEM (Fig. 5). The surface of the aluminum particle (Fig. 5a) was smooth and clean, whereas that of the graphene functionalized aluminum particle (Fig. 5b) was rough and covered with layers of graphene. The surface of the aluminum was smooth but graphene functionalized aluminum has rough surface can be attributed to the existence of the graphene and the reaction between the Al and the -PO(OH)₂.

Figure 5: FE-SEM image of the surface of aluminum particle (a) and graphene functionalized aluminum particle

3.3 Infrared emissivity and anticorrosive performance of G-Al coating

The weight concentration of the G-Al powder (or Al powder) in the coating is 40%. Fig.6 shows the infrared emissivity of Al powder and the graphene modified Al powder within 8~14 μm . The infrared emissivity of the coating with Al powder is 0.43, while the infrared emissivity of the coating with G-Al powder is 0.44. It can be seen that the infrared emissivity of pure and modified Al powder are similar. The results suggest that graphene cannot increase the infrared emissivity, because graphene has high electrical conductivity and low infrared emissivity.

Figure 6: The infrared emissivity of the Al and G-Al coating

To compare the anticorrosive performance, the samples of the Al and G-Al coating for testing infrared emissivity were measured by 500 hrs salt spray test. Fig. 7a is the picture of just putting two samples in the testing chamber. Fig. 7b and Fig. 7c shows the results of the salt spray test. The coating with G-Al powder remaining the appearance after 500 hrs of salt spray corrosion test, while the color of coating with the original aluminum powder has been changed in only 300 hrs.

Figure 7: The picture of coating salt spray test (a) before salt spray test (b) The coating with G-Al powder after 500 hrs salt spray test (c) The coating with Al powder after 300hrs salt spray test

4 CONCLUSIONS

GO was functionalized by reacting with 3-aminopropylphosphonic acid at 95 °C. XRD, FT-IR and XPS results confirm the grafting of 3-aminopropylphosphonic acid on the GO-P. G-Al powder was obtained through the reaction between Al and the $-PO(OH)_2$ of GO-P. The morphology of G-Al powder indicates that aluminum particles were successfully covered with layers of graphene. From the results of infrared emissivity and salt spray test, the coating using G-Al powder has not only low infrared emissivity, but also good anticorrosive performance.

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